

USMONKHOJA POLATHOJAYEV'S ROLE IN THE UZBEK NATIONAL AWAKENING

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Annotation: In this article, the emergence of the Jadidism movement, its place in the life of the Bukhara Emirate, the manifestations of the Jadidism movement, in particular, the role of Usmonkhoja Polathojhayev in these movements are highlighted. Also, the reforms in the field of education, the work carried out at different stages in the field of education and training were scientifically analyzed.

Key words: Jadidism, secularism, spirituality, enlightenment, education, science, innovation, advancement, literature, newspaper, magazine.

The Jadidism movement aimed to bolster national identity, overhaul the socio-political system, and secure independence for both the nation and the Motherland. Over the preceding centuries, traditional schools, which once nurtured numerous great minds, gradually disconnected from global progress. Thus, the paramount duty of contemporary intellectuals lay in revamping local educational institutions and establishing schools and universities that align with modern demands.

The main role of modern schools in educating the local people and the young generation, instilling the ideas of enlightenment into their minds, is educating the young generation in a scientific and enlightened manner. At the same time, the fact that they have fulfilled the responsible task of preparing mature and talented personnel for the society is really a great recognition and attention.

In recent times, notable transformations have occurred in the education sector under the leadership of our esteemed President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, particularly focusing on innovations and advancements. In his address to the parliament on January 24, 2020, the President addressed the imperative of reforming the education system, enhancing proficiency in the mother tongue, and elevating its standards, with a significant emphasis placed on literature. Among other things, the head of our state expressed the following thoughts about the past: "In general, we need to deeply study the legacy of the Jadidist

movement and our enlightened grandfathers. The more we study this spiritual treasure, the more we will find the correct answers to many questions that still concern us today. The more actively we promote this priceless wealth, the more our people, especially our youth, will realize the value of today's peaceful and free life" [1].

In the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, famous enlightened writers, scientists, state and public figures, who decided to raise the scientific fame of Bukhara and serve it well, grew up. Among them, local intellectuals such as Ahmed Donish, Mirza Salimbek, Haji Muhammad Ne'matullah Muhtaram, Sadriddin Aini, Abdurauf Fitrat, Usmonkhoja Polathojayev, Fayzulla Khojaev, Ubaidulla Khojaev, Mukammil Burkhanov, Otaulla Khojaev, Abdugadir Muhiddinov, Musa Saidjonov, who worked in various fields of science and left their names in history.

Now, let's talk about Usmonkhoja Polathojayev, who had an important place in the activity of Jadidism.

Usmonkhoja Polathojayev stands out as a notable figure within the Jadidist movement in Bukhara, recognized as both a distinguished state and public figure, as well as the chairman of Bukhara's Central Executive Committee (MIK). Born to Qori Polathoja, a prominent merchant from Bukhara, Usmonkhoja received his early education at a local madrasa before pioneering one of the earliest modern schools in the region.

Scant details are available regarding Usmonkhoja's life and endeavors from 1898 to 1910. Throughout this period, he played a pivotal role as a member and leader of the Jadidist movement, which gained traction across Turkestan. Usmonkhoja notably contributed to the founding of the modern Bukhara newspapers "Bukharai Sharif" and "Turon", demonstrating his commitment by sparing no expense in their publication. The Jadidist movement conducted educational campaigns in the cities of Amirlik such as Shahrisabz, Kitob, and Karki. Karki was significant not only for its cultural ties with the Russian Empire and Afghanistan but also for its importance in trade and commerce. In Karki city, under the initiative of Usmonkhoja, a new-style school was established in 1910. With the presence of a Russian military garrison in the city, Russian traders were granted the right to conduct trade freely. Usmonkhoja played a leading role among students who returned from studying in Turkey [2].

In the schools of the new method established by Usmonkhoja, special attention was paid to the following rules:

- divide children into classes according to their age;

- not to study more than 4-5 hours a day;
- take a 10-minute break between classes;
- focus on teaching secular subjects;
- literacy of students at the first stage;
- setting Friday and Sunday as rest days;
- After 10 months of education, giving students study holidays;
- examination of pupils;
- conducting classes in spacious and comfortable rooms;
- the use of binoculars, maps and globes.

According to the information given by the researcher Adey Kloden, Usmonkhoja Polathojayev brought various educational materials, maps, globes and European literature in Turkish from Turkey to Bukhara at his own expense [3].

As can be seen from the above information, the ideas of progress and enlightenment in the Emirate of Bukhara began to form in the second half of the 19th century and continued until the beginning of the 20th century. Elevating and developing these profound ideas inherited from Usmonkhoja Polathojayev has become one of the main goals of Young Bukharans.

In conclusion, it can be said that Usmonkhoja Polathojayev played an important role in the Bukhara resistance movement. At the beginning of the 20th century, young Bukharans worked to implement large-scale political reforms in the Emirate of Bukhara. The struggle of Bukhara's progressives for enlightenment in the conditions of the emirate system is also noteworthy. They established new method schools, published newspapers and magazines.

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